

APPLICATION OF REFRACTIVE INDEX IN THE STUDY OF CHEMICAL
CONSTITUTION. PART I. DETERMINATION OF TRANSITION
POINT OF CERTAIN HYDRATED INORGANIC SALTS IN
SOLUTION BY REFRACTIVE INDEX

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Refractive index determinations of aqueous solutions of hydrated inorganic salts of sodium carbonate between 20° and 50° and magnesium sulphate between 20° and 55° show abrupt change at certain temperatures. The transition points, thus determined, agree with the values determined by other methods.

Some inorganic salts, when crystallised out from aqueous solutions between certain temperature ranges, separate out with different amounts of water of crystallisation. The particular temperatures at which the degree of hydration changes have been found out by various methods; among these the solubility method has been used quite often. Other methods, such as, dilatometric, thermometric, viscometric, E.M.F. etc., have also been employed. The transition points, determined by different methods, are invariably quite close, though not always identical.

Uniform variations in the values of some physical properties of pure liquids have been noticed with rise of temperature, except at temperatures where changes in constitution take place. Salts in solution behave similarly. When solutions are heated to certain temperatures, their composition has been observed to change irregularly in values. This has been utilised for determination of their transition points. Thus, in case of sodium sulphate solutions, Gibson (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 496) from density measurements, and Glass and Madgine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1124) from viscosity determinations presumed the existence of different hydrates between certain temperature ranges by studying the variations in the values of these properties, although no marked change at the transition point was observed by them. Dunstan and Langton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 418) in the cases of saturated sodium sulphate and sodium carbonate solutions and Hartshorne (*ibid.*, 1924, 2096) in the cases of sodium sulphate, disodium hydrogen phosphate and nickel sulphate, however, found out the transition temperatures from viscosity determinations. Determination of refractive index is expected to yield similar information because the former is intimately connected with the density of the solution, the theory of which has been recently worked out by Sarkar and Palit (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1953, 27, 610).

During the present work determinations of refractive index of solutions of different concentrations of sodium chloride and sodium carbonate between 20° and 55° and of magnesium sulphate between 20° and 55° have been carried out. At certain temperatures in case of sodium carbonate and magnesium sulphate solutions, the variations were not regular; these corresponded with the transition temperatures.

In the case of sodium chloride solutions of four different concentrations (6M, 6M/5, 6M/25, 6M/125) the variation in the refractive index with rise of temperature, as noticed

by plotting temperature against n_D , is throughout regular within the range 20° - 50° . This shows the absence of changes in the composition of the salt in solution. In the literature also no change in the degree of hydration within this range appears to have been reported. [See graphs- I(b), Fig. 3 ; II(b) and III(b), Fig. 1 ; and IV(b), Fig. 4].

FIG. 1

FIG. 3

FIG. 2

In the case of aqueous sodium carbonate solutions of four different concentrations ($8M/5$, $2M/5$, $2M/25$, $2M/125$) it has been observed that abnormal changes in the regular variation of values take place in case of concentrated and moderately concentrated solutions ($8M/5$, $2M/5$, $2M/25$), once at 31.8° to 32° and again at 34.2° to 34.6° ; in the case of dilute solution ($2M/125$), once at 32° and then again at 35.4° . This shows that at certain temperatures the composition of the salt changes in aqueous solution. These transition temperatures appear to be slightly influenced by concentration, as in the case of the dilute solution the second transition point is 35.4° , whereas in the more concentrated solutions it is 34.2° to 34.6° [vide graphs II(a) and III(a), Fig. 1 ; I(a), Fig. 2 and IV(a), Fig. 4].

FIG. 5

FIG. 4

Previous workers obtained by using mostly the solubility or viscometric methods similar values for transition points of different hydrates. Some of these are: (a) 32° the transition point between deca and heptahydrate, 35.4° between hepta and monohydrate (Richards and Fiske, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **36**, 485); (b) 32° between deca and stable heptahydrate, 35.37° between hepta and monohydrate and 32.96° , the metastable transition point between deca and monohydrated carbonates (Wells and McAdam, *ibid.*, 1907, **29**, 721); (c) 34° approximately (Tilden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1884, **45**, 268); (d) 32.5° between deca and heptahydrate, 35.4° between deca and monohydrate (Dunstan and Langton, *loc. cit.*).

In the case of the four aqueous magnesium sulphate solutions (M , $M/5$, $M/25$, $M/125$) also, refractive index determinations show that the transition in the composition of the salt is influenced by the temperature as also by the concentration. Two transition points, 42° and 49.4° , are observed for the nearly saturated solution (M), while only one, 49.4° , for the less concentrated solutions ($M/5$, $M/25$, $M/125$) [vide graphs-I(c), Fig. 2; II(c) and III(c), Fig. 1; and IV(c), Fig 5]. Some of the transition points quoted in the literature are: (a) 50° between heptahydrate and labile or β -hexahydrate (Wiedmann, *Wied. Ann.*, 1882, **17**, 571); (b) 48° to 48.5° between hepta and hexahydrate (Vander Heide, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1893, **12**, 418); (c) 48.4° between hepta and hexahydrate (Carpenter and Jette, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 578).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Sodium chloride, anhydrous sodium carbonate and crystalline magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were all of A.R. quality (B.D.H.) and the same sample of conductivity water was used in all determinations. Concentrated solutions of each of them were prepared and other solutions were obtained by dilution. The refractive index was measured using a critical angle refractometer (Bellingham and Stanley Ltd.), the micrometer of which could read angle up to one second. Sodium lamp was used as the source of light in all measurements. The accuracy of the instrument was tested by measuring the refractive index of water, *n*-heptane and *n*-octane. The temperature of the solution under measurement was controlled within $\pm 0.2^\circ$ by allowing thermostated water of the requisite temperature to flow through the jacket of the apparatus, surrounding the solution in the cell over the mounted prism. The readings at each temperature were taken after maintaining the particular temperature for at least 15 minutes. The n_D' , calculated out at various temperatures and graphs of refractive index of the solutions against temperature were plotted (Figs. 1-5).

Preliminary investigations with sodium sulphate and zinc sulphate have shown similar results. Further work is in progress, and attempts are being made to determine the composition of the salt while in solution at either side of the transition point. Nevertheless, there is a similarity regarding the transition point, at which the salt in solution and the solid hydrated salt undergo change in the degree of hydration.

The determination of refractive index of solution of salts of different concentrations provides an easy approach towards the study of composition changes with variation of temperature.

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Received February 4, 1955.